

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE: THEORY AND METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: *The methodology and theory of teaching foreign languages are the focus of the research. The article defines terms related to cross-cultural communication, foreign language teaching (FLT), conventional and current approaches to teaching. The study’s authors view the project teaching technique as one of the most successful techniques for teaching foreign languages.*

Key words: *approach, methodology, qualification, interdisciplinary, education, teaching theory, technique.*

Modern didactics focus on making education more effective in general and in foreign languages in particular. Globalization is a concept that has become popular in recent years. It is the idea that the world is gradually coming together into a single economy and culture due to advances in communication and technology, and the influence of large multinational companies [There are many advantages to working for a global corporation, such as increasing the quality of education and qualifications, increasing industrial mobility between industries, and increasing migratory processes that reduce national barriers and promote globalization of the economy. This attracts people to work for them and requires them to learn different languages. Education and employment are heavily influenced by the economy. Sometimes this can be problematic because of uneven economic development across different countries; people have to move abroad to find work or education that suits them. This is another reason why people study foreign languages, foreign cultures, and foreign histories. International educational and professional migration is facilitated by transnational corporations and uneven economies.

Since the turn of the twenty-first century, the socio-cultural context of foreign language learning in the world has changed significantly; the professions’ professional significance in the labor market as a whole, as well as their educational and self-educational functions in schools and universities, have increased, which has led to an increase in motivation to learn foreign languages [4]. Due to the increased use of foreign languages in the twenty-first century, the methodology and theory of FLT

should be improved and developed in accordance with current trends in the development of society, economy, and industry.

Learning the foundations of foreign language teaching theory and methodology is the aim of the research.

Methodology

Teaching methodology is a complex of sciences that study the ways in which the teacher and students engage in orderly, interconnected activities with the goal of solving educational problems. It encompasses both traditional and innovative teaching methods. The methodology of FLT reasonably incorporates data from basic and related sciences in solving theoretical and practical issues of training, avoiding one-sided orientation to any one science [6]. Methodology as a science is based on the educational process, the components of which are: teaching activities of a teacher, training (goals, content, methods, technique).

Learning theory is a field of pedagogy that studies how people assimilate knowledge, skills, and abilities; how they function as trainers for different kinds of activities; how content, methods, and organizational forms of teaching are taught; and how the educational process affects the people who participate in it [2]. A principle is a useful way to express the pedagogical idea of recognized laws and regularities in the activity categories. It conveys knowledge about the objectives, nature, and structure of instruction in a way that makes it possible to use it as a set of guidelines for best practices. One fundamental area within the methodology that provides insight into the perspectives of language researchers and the teaching process is the approach to learning. A teaching approach is based on the linguistic foundations of learning and the didactic foundations of learning, which are the relevant theories of language and learning, respectively [1]. Foreign language teaching theory and methodology is the science that looks at the objectives and contents, pedagogical strategies, and methods and materials of teaching foreign languages [7]. The theory and methodology of teaching foreign languages (FLT) includes teaching about other countries' customs, history, and cultures in addition to teaching grammar and writing in a foreign language [6]. The fundamental sciences used in foreign language instruction include linguistics, pedagogy, didactics, psychology, and psycholinguistics.

There are different methods of FLT:

The term "classical method" also refers to the Grammar translation technique. This approach was developed in response to the desire of Westerners to study "foreign" languages like Greek and Latin.

1) Grammar rules, vocabulary memorization, including different declensions and conjugations, text translation, and completing written exercises were the main objectives of GTM [9].

2) Direct Methodology. The fundamental tenet of the Direct Method was that second language acquisition ought to resemble first language acquisition. The approach would involve little to no analysis of grammar rules, a lot of oral interaction, spontaneous language use, and no translation between the first and second languages [9].

3) Teaching Language Through Communication. The teaching of language can take many forms. One is known as CLT, or Communicative Language Teaching. This learner-centered approach prioritizes communication and practical scenarios [9].

The audio-lingual method, also known as the army method, the aural-oral method, or the new key, is a method of teaching foreign languages that involves having students mimic and repeat regular patterns and dialogues from daily life through a series of drills. During the 1950s and 1960s, the Audio-lingual Method firmly dominated the field of education [9]. There are many well-established and highly successful approaches to teaching foreign languages; however, the advancement of modern society necessitates the search for and application of increasingly sophisticated techniques and tools. Multilingualism is becoming the norm. Novel approaches are needed to ensure that learning foreign languages quickly and effectively. These methods should concentrate on improving the target language.

Multinational corporations operate in a world where innovative communication and information technologies are unimaginable. The project method is among the most effective strategies.

Positive outcomes are seen when the project methodology is used in English classes, even when it is part of the curriculum:

- 1) Students learn a foreign language well.
- 2) Students can put the knowledge they have learned in computer science classes into practice.
- 3) Students are aware of the importance of interdisciplinary relationships.

There are several benefits that the project method offers over conventional teaching techniques.

1) Boost students' motivation when learning a foreign language is one of the main benefits.

2) The visual integration of knowledge across multiple disciplines or subjects in educational settings.

3) There's lots of room for inspiring and imaginative pursuits [3].

In the globalized world of multinational corporations that combine national economies, one should conclude that people need to learn about the cultures, histories, and languages of other countries. On the one hand, FLT is necessary to accomplish this through the development of creative and universal teaching methods. On the other hand, there are also effective FLT (project-based learning) strategies that can be implemented in the current educational environment.

References:

1. Bekarevich, T. I. The concept of «approach» in theoretical research on the methodology of teaching foreign languages in primary and secondary schools. – 2012 – pp. 314 – 315. – Text: electronic. URL: <https://moluch.ru/conf/ped/archive/21/1507/>
2. Borytko N. M. Theory of learning. – 2006 – P. 3. – Text: electronic.– URL:http://window.edu.ru/resource/325/63325/files/Teoriya_obucheniya.pdf 316
3. Kuznetsova S. The use of the project methods at the lessons of English. – 2014 – pp.12 – 13. – Text: electronic. – URL: <https://nsportal.ru/shkola/inostrannyeyazyki/angliiskiy-yazyk/library/2014/02/22/statya-metod-proektov-v-obuchenii>
4. Сафоева, С. (2015). Влияние психологических и возрастных особенностей младших школьников на овладение иностранного языка. *Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов*, (4), 112-114
5. Lectures on the Theory and methodology of teaching a foreign language Text: electronic. – URL: <https://infourok.ru/lekcii-po-teorii-i-metodike-obucheniyainostrannomu-yaziku-481575.html>
6. Sadokat Safoyeva, [СОГЛАСОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЯ СУЩЕСТВЕННОГО И ПРИЛАГАЮЩЕГО ЛЕКСЕМА В УЗБЕКСКОМ И АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ](https://buxdu.uz/maqola-va-tezislar/2021/5/5/sohlasovatelnye-znacheniya-sushtvennogo-i-priLAGAyushchego-leksema-v-uzbekskom-i-angliyskom-yazyke), [ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ \(buxdu.uz\)](https://buxdu.uz/): Том 5 № 5 (2021): [Maqola va tezislar \(buxdu.uz\)](https://buxdu.uz/maqola-va-tezislar)
7. Methods of teaching English language (2.2.3 Using project method in teaching a foreign language) – Text: electronic. – URL: https://knowledge.allbest.ru/languages/2c0b65635b3bd79a5d43a88521306d37_0.html
8. Methods of teaching foreign languages as a scientific field – Text: electronic. – URL: https://studme.org/167135/pedagogika/metodika_obucheniya_inostrannym_yazykam_nauchnaya_oblast

9. Methods of teaching foreign languages as a science. Subject and methods of research– Text: electronic. – URL: <https://lektsii.org/18-27322.html> 8. Method of teaching in pedagogy: disclosure of the concept – Text: electronic. – URL: <https://zachnik.com/spravochnik/pedagogika/teorija-obucheniya/metodobucheniya-v-pedagogike/>

10.Sadokat Safoyeva, [TEXT-REALITY INTEGRATION AND SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF LITERARY TEXT](#), [ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ \(buxdu.uz\)](#): Том 26 № 26 (2022): Статьи и тезисы (buxdu.uz)

11.Sadokat Safoyeva, [LINGUISTICS FEATURES OF THE PUBLISTIC STYLE](#), [ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ \(buxdu.uz\)](#): Том 5 № 5 (2021): [Maqola va tezislar \(buxdu.uz\)](#)